

A Review of Neural Networking Methodology to Different Aspects of Electrical Power Systems

Wafi Danesh

Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering
American International University - Bangladesh (AIUB)
Dhaka, Bangladesh
E-mail: mail4wafi@yahoo.com

Nomir Muktadir

Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering
American International University - Bangladesh (AIUB)
Dhaka, Bangladesh
E-mail: n.muktadir@yahoo.com

Sandip Bhowmick

Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering
American International University - Bangladesh (AIUB)
Dhaka, Bangladesh
E-mail: bh_sandip@ymail.com

Md. Shamaul Alam

Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering
American International University - Bangladesh (AIUB)
Dhaka, Bangladesh
E-mail: shamaul.alam@yahoo.com

Abstract—There is an ever increasing consumer base in the electrical power industry and with the rapid advancement in the field of electricity generation, electricity can now be supplied to many underdeveloped areas in impoverished locations, previously considered difficult or inaccessible. Along with this expansion, there is also the growing use of semiconductor electronic and solid state switching devices in everyday life. These devices are nonlinear loads and therefore produce severe distortions in the power flow. Providing a solution to the variety of problems that result from these applications requires the estimation and accurate analysis of the multitude of data available. The most pressing of these problems, as has been found surveyed in recent decades, are load forecasting, estimation of harmonics, fault detection, economic dispatch, security assessment and voltage stability analysis. A great many methods of analysis of these problems have been proposed, mainly statistical ones. However, in recent times, artificial intelligence techniques have gained popularity in this field, most notably the method of neural networking (NN). The popularity of neural networks lie in their speed, accuracy and learning ability in the case where a mathematical relation cannot be established. In lieu of the number of applications of neural networks in power systems, this paper provides an outline and brief descriptions of the proposed methods of analysis of the problems mentioned above.

Keywords-neural network; multi-layer perceptron; back propagation algorithm; pattern recognition; radial basis function network

I. INTRODUCTION

Neural Network (NN) is a system loosely modeled on the human brain. An ANN can be seen as a union of simple processing units, called neurons that are interconnected to each other through connections similar to synapses. This is analogous to the many thousands of neurons that are interwoven constituting a complex web of connections in the

human brain. Neural networks have found uses in a broad range of applications including pattern classification, pattern recognition, optimization, prediction and automatic control. In essence of the multitude of applications that involve many different structures of these networks, they are known by many names such as connectionism, parallel distributed processing, neurocomputing, natural intelligent systems, machine learning algorithms, and artificial neural networks. Nowadays with the rise in global population and its subsequent effect on the economy, there is a rapid growth in the number of nonlinear loads in electrical power systems. The continuous supply of electrical power has become a challenge for these power utilities. In the face of these challenges, efficient analysis tools for electrical power systems have been developed. Till date, neural networking has been the most popular and effective of these tools.

The general structure of the neural network is divided into three layers: the input layer, the output layer and one or more hidden layers consisting of neurons. In the input layer, a set of data is used to train the network, which is processed in the hidden layer to produce a desired outcome in the output layer. The main advantage of these networks is their ability to quickly and correctly establish and generalize a relationship between various sets of input and output data, which may otherwise be unknown.

This paper presents an investigation into the many aspects of the electrical power distribution network where neural networking is widely used. It is followed by brief discussions about the most important sectors of neural networking applications in the power system, as determined from the results of studies carried out [1].

Artificial neural networks (ANN) have found many potential applications in the control and operation of power systems recently [2].

The following categories are the most popular sections of the power system analysis where neural network applications have been mostly concentrated in recent years:

- Load forecasting.
- Estimation of harmonics.
- Fault detection.
- Voltage stability analysis.
- Security assessment.
- Economic dispatch.

systems, this paper has focused on the above mentioned subjects.

II. VARIOUS ANN APPLICATIONS IN POWER SYSTEMS

A. Load Forecasting

Probably the most important factor in the economic and efficient operation of a power system is the ability to predict in advance, the load on the system. There are variations in the frequency of electrical power consumption throughout certain durations such as a week, a month or a year. This is due to many social and cultural factors such as holidays, religious festivals etc. Load forecasting enables the management to acquire vital information about the distribution of the power supply among the various loads, and which section of the consumer base will have high and low demands at a certain period in time. Therefore, the power supply can be diverted from areas where there is a low demand to areas where there may be an urgent requirement. It also assists in taking decisions about the future development and expansion of the existing power supply. Overall, the load forecasting analysis is divided into three classes [3]:

Short-term load forecasting: The duration of short-term load forecasting is usually a twenty four hour period. However, this is not fixed and can be elongated as deemed necessary to the prevailing situation. The period can be stretched to a few days or perhaps a week. Information obtained from short-term forecasting helps in diversion of the electricity supply from areas of low consumption, real time control, unit commitment of the generating devices etc.

Mid-term load forecasting: The duration of mid-term load forecasting is generally from a month to several years, and is necessary for calculation of the fuel cost and electricity tariffs.

Long-term forecasting: The duration of long-term load forecasting normally spans quite a few years, somewhat in the range of seven to eighteen. Essentially this type of forecasting is required to determine the size and scope of future expansion and reduction of fixed and varying costs.

Out of the three classes of load forecasting mentioned above, neural network applications have been mostly concentrated to short and long-term forecasting. All of the classes are analyzed using a multi-layered feed forward network (MLFFN), which is also known as a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) network, with a back propagation (BP) algorithm.

In long-term load forecasting, alongside the multi-layer perceptron network method, other back propagation methods such as radial basis function network (RBFN) and recurrent neural network (RNN) are also used [4]. A comparison of the ease of use of the three methods mentioned has revealed that the radial basis function network gives more accurate forecast results.

Figure 1: Classification of papers on ANN applications in power systems

To assist in the development of more efficient and robust neural networks to solve a broader range of problems in power

Among the three classes, short-term load forecasting has had the greatest concentration of neural network applications, because of its frequent use owing to the short time span. The main method of neural networking, as stated before, is the multi-layer perceptron with a back propagation algorithm. In recent times, a time series forecasting model has been introduced into the back propagation model to give better approximations [5]. There has also been used a new technique in short-term load forecasting, which is the support vector machine (SVM) [6]. Support vector machines give forecasting results much faster and more accurately.

B. Estimation of Harmonics

Due to the advent of newer semiconductor electronic devices at present and their subsequent introduction into the consumer load base, the percentage of non-linear loads is increasing rapidly. An increasing number of these semiconductor devices are solid state switching devices, which introduce harmonics into the power systems at the time of switching [7]. Along with the use of solid state devices, the increasing use of converters also contributes to the introduction of harmonics in the power system. The converters are mostly used to either alter the frequency of the supply voltage or transform the AC supply into a DC supply, thus resulting in harmonic distortions. Another reason for the contamination of the supply voltage with harmonics is the fact that all modern power systems function at the upper limit of the voltage supplied, which causes the number of harmonics in the current to increase as the saturation of the transformers is reached. Some of the most frequent difficulties created by harmonic distortion in power distribution networks in electrical power systems are:

- Over voltage
- Circuit breaker tripping
- Malfunction and erroneous operation of equipment
- Interference with communication
- Cable heating
- Data recording and metering problems
- Breakdown of insulation

In order to ameliorate the effects of harmonic distortions in the supply voltage, it is necessary to design special filters. For the construction of these filters, it is necessary to determine the magnitude and phase angle of the harmonics. The use of artificial neural networks provides a fast and efficient method of computation for harmonics, along with the ability to establish and generalize a relationship between the various input quantities which might be unknown [8]. Furthermore, the computations are also performed in real-time, which is an added advantage. The most widely used neural networking methods for harmonic estimation are the Fourier Neural Network (FNN) and Feed Forward Back Propagation Artificial Neural Network (FFBP ANN). Among the two methods mentioned, the FFBP ANN method gives the more precise estimation, with accuracy of the order of 95%. Compared to other methods such as Fast Fourier Transform (FFT), genetic algorithm (GA), hybrid genetic algorithm –

least square (GA-LS), hybrid particle swarm optimization – least square (PSO- LS), artificial neural networks are still the most reliable for harmonics estimation.

C. Fault detection

The occurrence of a fault is one of the most critical issues pertaining to the safety and operation of an electrical power distribution system, as a large number of equipment such as generators; transformers etc. can be severely damaged. Electrical power systems are comprised of varying, perplex and intricately designed interacting elements, where a possibility of occurrence of a disturbance or fault is perennial. With the emergence of massive power generating stations and increasingly interconnected power systems, early fault detection and almost instantaneous isolation of the faulty section is paramount to maintaining system stability. Previously, techniques and methodology related to fault diagnosis were concerned with the post-fault period and dealt with the aftermath of fault occurrence. However, early fault detection (EFD) methods were developed which provided better power system protection by warning operators prior to a fault and locating the disruptive region [9]. Artificial neural networks, to date, have provided the most efficient fault detection procedure. ANN can be trained to adapt themselves to various statistical distributions of data and non-linear mappings. Currents measured at the specific relay points are subject to alterations when a fault occurs on a transmission line. This is the basis upon which the principle of fault detection and classification is founded. The variation of current signals preceding and following the fault is used to design an ANN-based fault detector or classifier module for fault detection and classification [10]. The parallel structure of neural networks allows ‘incipient fault detection’ which is an indication of an increase in the lead time for detecting faults. Neural networks allow for a greater degree of fault tolerance than conventional fault detection methods because there are many more processing nodes, each with primarily local connections. The malfunction of a few nodes does not drastically affect overall performance. In addition, neural networks are non-parametric and therefore cannot make good assumptions about the character of their probability distributions of the sensor measurements. Artificial neural networks can learn and store information about fault occurrence through associative memory and thus have an associative diagnostic ability with respect to the faults that occur in a power system. The method of artificial neural networks can therefore predict and locate faults with an accuracy of about 95% to 98%.

D. Voltage stability analysis

Electrical power systems are the most valuable assets of modern civilization, and as such the need for their operation and maintenance cannot be underscored. If a failure were to result, the consequences will be far reaching and felt in other key sectors of the economy such as industry, transportation, financial to name a few. The last few decades have witnessed

quite a fast pace of deregulation of the power sector, and as a result of this, the consumer base has increased to include more people. In many cases, due to a shortage of funding or other factors as environmental concerns, the expansion of the electrical power network has been limited, forcing many modern day power systems to operate near the peripheries of their stability limits. There has thus been an increase in the probability of voltage collapse, which is the uncontrollable drop in potential resulting from the inability of the power system to compensate for reactive power shortages after faults, disturbances or due to excessive loading of the power system. Electrical power system voltage stability is therefore, one of the most daunting tasks for power utility companies. Online voltage stability monitoring is an integral part of the modern day energy management systems (EMS), and artificial neural networks have till present, been the most efficient computational technique for voltage stability analysis [11].

Artificial neural networks have attained great acclaim from researchers in recent years as a tool for online voltage stability assessment, due to the non-linearity of the voltage stability assessment problem. The main step to analyzing the voltage stability problem is to evaluate the distance from the actual point of operation to the voltage collapse point. ANN accomplishes this task by going through the following steps:

- Choosing the type of ANN
- Choosing the topology of the ANN
- Selecting an input variable set for the ANN
- Selection of the activation function of the neuron
- Choosing the learning algorithm

The multi-layer feed-forward neural network (MLFFN), also known as multi-layer perceptron, is the most widely used neural network model for voltage stability analysis, because of its successes in solving a diverse and complex range of problems, by training themselves in supervision with a back propagation algorithm. The following flowchart describes the steps in an ANN based monitoring system for voltage system stability:

Figure 2: ANN based monitoring system for voltage system stability flow chart

There exists, however, a drawback of using artificial neural networks for voltage stability analysis. In general, there is an incredibly large amount of input data for typical power systems and this limits the use of ANN, because the functional relationship itself gets changed from one topology to another. To overcome these setbacks, it is necessary that the most important of these data are selected so as to obtain a compact and efficient ANN. Under these circumstances, many feature reduction methods, such as the “Principal Component Analysis (PCA)” methods have been developed. Despite the use of these feature reduction methods, more than one neural network is still required for computation. This further debacle is solved by using a radial basis function network (RBFN), which has been proposed recently. It can perform with only a single layer for all numbers of input data and contingencies [12].

E. Security assessment

Due to the imposition of various conditions on the power systems following certain economic, environmental and technical factors, they are forced to run near their operational limits. As a result, there is a much greater probability of disturbances which can lead to service interruption to consumers and collapse of the system. Therefore, a fast and accurate security supervision method is necessary for safe operation of the power system. To that end, neural networks have been a reliable source of computation. Security assessment (SA) means the analysis required to determine if a power system can achieve particular reliability and security criteria in both transient or dynamic and steady-state time frames for all likely contingencies or disturbances. Since the primary task of an electric power system is to deliver power to the consumers without exceeding acceptable voltage and frequency limits, a method of fast computation in contingencies is crucial. The task has to be solved in real time and in a safe, reliable and economical manner [13].

Generally, there are two types of security assessments: static security assessment and dynamic security assessment.

1) Static Security Assessment (SSA)

The static security assessment of a power system considers whether, following a disturbance, the power system goes to a steady state operating condition that remains within the operating constraints of the given system. The constraints ensure that the power is properly balanced within the network, the magnitude of all bus voltages is within acceptable limits, and the thermal limit of each transmission line is not exceeded so as not to cause overheating of the transmission lines. Violation of any one of these constraints, may result in a “black out” or collapse of the system. The electrical power system thus becomes insecure.

2) Dynamic Security Assessment (DSA)

Dynamic security assessment refers to the analysis required to ascertain whether or not a power system can attain specified reliability and security criteria in both transient and steady

state time frames for all likely and possible contingencies. In the usual functioning environment, the system is considered secure, if the operating criteria prior to and following contingency conditions are met. Online DSA takes measurements of the actual system condition and performs security analysis in near real time and conveys subsequent information about the results to the operator or directly onto control systems.

Figure 3: Data flow in power system operation

Fig. 3 is a flowchart of the principle data flow in a power system where real-time measurements are stored in a database. The state estimation then adjusts bad and missing data. Based on these estimations, the current mathematical model of the power system is established and furthermore, depending on the simulations of potential equipment outages, the security level of the system is determined. In both types of security assessment scenarios, different operational states are defined:

- Normal or secure state: In the normal state, all consumer demands are met and operation is within prescribed limits.
- Alert or critical state: In this state, all system variables remain within limits and constraints are not violated. However, slight disruption can lead towards instability.
- Emergency or insecure state: In this state, the emergency mode of operation commences upon violation of inequality constraints pertaining to security. For a 3-bus-3-line power system that is shown in Fig. 4, considering limitations,

the operating and constrained spaces are illustrated in the figure.

Real life power systems have a large dimension of operation, and so to overcome this problem and choose the type of neural network, its learning algorithm and adjusting their parameters, three main approaches are considered:

- Limitations of the number of contingences and characterization of the security boundaries. It is mostly the case with supervised neural networks like multi-layer perceptron.
- Reduction in the dimension of the operating vector. It is the case with unsupervised NN like Oja-Sanger networks.
- Quantification of the operating point into a reduced number of classes. It is the case with clustering algorithms such as the nearest neighbor or the k-means clustering algorithms.

Figure 4: Three-bus three-line power system

Pattern recognition (PR) approach is used in neural networking models for security assessment. The models primarily used for classification are multi-layer perceptron, learning vector quantization (LVQ), probabilistic neural network (PNN) and adaptive resonance theory mapping (ARTMAP). Most commonly used among them is the multi-layer perceptron with back propagation algorithm, due to its online learning capability. A comparison of the simulation results for these models show that classifiers with high levels of accuracy and less false dismissal rate can only be realized with PNN and ARTMAP classifiers as they involve less time, making them suitable for real time security monitoring and evaluation [14].

F. Economic dispatch

Economic dispatch (ED) of power generating units has always been a key factor in the economic operation of electrical power systems. It is a computational process whereby the total

required generation is distributed among the many generation units in operation, by minimizing the selected cost criterion, which is subject to load and operational constraints. For any specified load condition, ED determines the power output of each plant, along with that of the generating unit within each plant. It is used in real-time energy management power system control by most programs for allocation of the total generation among the operational units, focusing upon coordination of the production cost within all power plants operating on the system.

The main goal of economic dispatch consists of minimizing the operating costs depending on demand and subject to certain constraints, such as allocation of the required load demand between the operational generation units. In practice, the entire unit operating range is not always available for load allocation due to physical operational limits. Economic Dispatch is carried out to calculate an optimal generation distribution policy, taking into account various operational factors. Several tools have been developed for analysis of economic dispatch, namely Lagrangian relaxation method, linear programming(LP) techniques, dynamic programming(DP), Beale's quadratic programming, Newton-Raphson's economic method, interior point method, mixed integer programming, network flow programming, Lagrangian augmented function, and lastly genetic algorithms and neural networks. Neural networks, especially the Hopfield Neural Network and modified versions of it, have to this day remained the most popular among all.

Hopfield Neural Network is a simple artificial network which is able to store certain memories or patterns in a manner rather similar to the brain - the full pattern can be recovered if the network is presented with only partial or incomplete information. Applied to economic dispatch problems, it gives very promising results. However, the unit commitment problem cannot be solved within the frame work of conventional Hopfield networks, because both discrete and continuous terms need to be fully modeled to the program. This drawback is solved with a new method known as Augmented Hopfield network, which shows an interconnection between the neurons giving the more general energy function both discrete and continuous terms. This is based on genetic algorithm and fuzzy systems [15].

The main setback of Hopfield neural network is its low converging speed, which can be somewhat ameliorated by decreasing the limitations, except in nonlinear cases, where this method is not recommended [16].

III. CONCLUSION

This paper presents the utilization of neural networking in electrical power systems along with the specific aspects of the power system where its application has been concentrated. The popularity of neural networks stems from the following factors:

- ability to incorporate increasing amounts of data for processing whilst dealing with stochastic variations of the scheduled operating point
- rapid online processing and classification of data
- capability for non-linear modeling and filtering of system data and learning ability in cases where a mathematical relation cannot be established

In the case of power system analysis, however, neural networks are to be regarded as an extra tool or different technique, rather than being a replacement for both conventional artificial intelligence (AI) and nonartificial intelligence based power system procedures. Neural networks still rely on conventional simulations for producing training vectors and their corresponding analysis, especially if the data is with a large degree of noise. Some major improvements still need to be made for neural networking: training time, choice of training vectors, upgrading of trained nets and integration of newer technology.

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Wafi Danesh completed his Bachelor of Science in Electrical and Electronic Engineering from American International University- Bangladesh in 2011. His research interests lie in the field of neuro fuzzy networks, piezoelectricity, renewable energy and optical electronics. He is working as an engineer in "Sweet Dreams Development". Mr. Wafi is a student member of the IEEE.

Sandip Bhowmick completed his Bachelor of Science in Electrical and Electronic Engineering from American International University- Bangladesh in 2010. His research interests lie in the field of networking and telecommunications, and power systems protection. He is working as an Executive in Service Section in "Source & Service" Bangladesh.

Nomir Muktadir completed his Bachelor of Science in Electrical and Electronic Engineering from American International University- Bangladesh in 2011. His research interests lie in the field of neuro-fuzzy networks, VHDL modeling and logic synthesis and artificial intelligence.

Md. Shamaul Alam is in his final semester of Bachelor of Science in Electrical and Electronic Engineering in American International University- Bangladesh. His research interests lie in the field of networking and telecommunications, electrical machines and photonics.